

Cost-effectiveness and budget impact analyses of Typhoid Vi capsular polysaccharide vaccination in Indonesia

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Abstract

Typhoid fever has a substantial economic impact in developing countries, including in Indonesia. As the most cost-effective intervention to prevent typhoid fever, vaccination has not yet been introduced in the country. This study aimed to analyse the cost-effectiveness and budget impact of typhoid vaccination strategies, focusing on high-burden regions in Indonesia.

This study applied a top-down cost analysis method by collecting costs from various sources to estimate incremental cost-effectiveness ratio and to analyse the impact of this new program in a time horizon of six years within the scenario. In the first five years, the typhoid vaccine will be introduced only in high-risk areas, with nationwide vaccination starting in the sixth year.

The results showed that vaccination can prevent 158,276 cases and 352 deaths in six years. It also could save treatment costs up to \$10,655,063, resulting in a cost-saving intervention. Compared with the routine immunization budget, the total budget for typhoid vaccination would be 0.11%, 0.15%, 0.18%, 0.86%, 1.21% and 2.11%.

To conclude, the nationwide typhoid vaccination in Indonesia is a cost-saving and affordable intervention since the required budget was only 2.11% of Indonesia's total routine immunization budget.

Keywords

Top-down cost analysis, incremental cost-effectiveness ratio, cost saving, affordable

Introduction

Typhoid fever is an acute systemic infection caused by the highly virulent and invasive intestinal bacterium *Salmonella typhi* (*S. typhi*). Typhoid fever is a widespread public health problem, especially in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) (WHO 2018). Global estimates of the burden of typhoid fever are estimated at 11–21 million

people infected and approximately 145,000–161,000 deaths annually. Over the past two decades, a consistent finding from typhoid disease burden studies is that typhoid fever incidence is high in South and Southeast Asia, with significant heterogeneity within countries in age-specific and geographic incidence (WHO 2017).

Typhoid fever is endemic in Indonesia and threatens public health, requiring severe attention from various

directions. The problem is further complicated by an increase in carriers, relapse, and antibiotic resistance, complicating treatment and prevention efforts. In 2008, Indonesia reported a typhoid fever incidence rate of 81.7 per 100,000 people, with the age of 2–15 is the most affected group (Elisabeth Purba et al. 2016).

The challenges faced by the Indonesian typhoid fever control program in preventing and reducing typhoid fever incidence are: (i) increasing carrier or relapse and antibiotic resistance (Ministry of Health 2006), (ii) most of the inhabitants still have limited access to clean water, (iii) low levels of clean and healthy housing behavior in the community and limited availability of good sanitation facilities, (iv) poverty rate and economic inequality remains high, (v) several places selling food that does not meet health requirements (Ministry of Health 2023), (vi) increased transport and population movement from one region/country to another to various destinations, causing the transmission of typhoid fever increased and complicating efforts to control it (WHO 2018), and (vii) typhoid vaccination is not yet part of the national immunization program in Indonesia. Until now, the use of typhoid vaccines has been limited to several private doctors' practices and private hospitals (Elisabeth Purba et al. 2016).

The World Health Organization (WHO) emphasizes the introduction of new-generation typhoid conjugate vaccines should be prioritized in countries with the highest typhoid disease or a high burden of antimicrobial-resistant *S. typhi* (WHO 2018). The Vi polysaccharide vaccine (ViPS) comprises Vi capsular polysaccharides purified from the Ty2 *S. typhi* strain (Levine et al. 1999). The vaccine reaches a certain level of protection within two to three weeks after administration and can be administered to people aged two years and older. The vaccine is available in a 0.5 ml prefilled syringe containing 25 micrograms of Vi antigen in isotonic phenol buffer. The vaccine is administered intramuscularly into the deltoid muscle. Revaccination is done every three years (Klugman 1987; Froeschle and Decker 2010; FDA and Sanofi Pasteur 2014). A single dose of the ViPS vaccine induces high levels of her IgG anti-Vi antibodies in the serum (Klugman 1987). In pre-licensure studies in Nepal and China, vaccine efficacy was 72% [95%CI: 42–86] and 69% [95%CI: 28] at 17 and 19 months, respectively (Acharya 1987; Yang et al. 2001). In a post-licensure cluster randomized trial conducted in India, ViPs vaccine efficacy in children aged 2 to 4 years was 80% [95% CI: 53–91] (Sur et al. 2009).

Previous economic evaluations have demonstrated the cost-effectiveness of typhoid ViPS vaccination in high-incidence areas in Asia. In some cases, vaccinating the most affected age groups proved significantly more cost-effective (Cook et al. 2008). However, no health technology assessment in Indonesia includes typhoid vaccine products in national immunization programs. To effectively control typhoid fever through vaccination, it is crucial to conduct an economic evaluation study of typhoid ViPS vaccination in Indonesia. This study aimed to analyse the cost-effectiveness and budget impact of typhoid vaccination strategies from the payer's perspective in a six-year time horizon, focusing on high-burden regions in Indonesia.

Materials and methods

A cost-effectiveness and budget impact model was developed by considering data published by BPS-Statistics Indonesia for the population coverage and prevalence data based on the National Basic Health Researcha decision tree model of health intervention outcome was developed to assess the cost-effectiveness of the typhoid vaccine (Fig. 1).

This decision tree model compared the outcomes of typhoid vaccination versus no vaccination within the same cohort, using prevalence data to guide the analysis. In the vaccination scenario, some individuals might avoid typhoid entirely, while others might still have the disease, leading to recovery or mortality. Without vaccination, individuals faced a higher risk of typhoid infection, with outcomes including recovery or mortality. The model assisted in quantifying the morbidity and mortality cases avoided through vaccination while estimating the costs of vaccination versus the costs of treating typhoid cases without vaccination. In this model, a one-time typhoid vaccination program with a gradual introduction targeting different regions in Indonesia was designed and analysed. Revaccination was excluded from the analysis to focus solely on the impact of a single vaccination round. The model aimed to evaluate this approach's health and economic outcomes and assess its potential adaptation into a routine immunization program. Ultimately, the model could analyse the morbidity and mortality cases avoided, providing a comprehensive understanding of the vaccine's impact.

The formula used for this analysis was:

$$It = I0 \times (1 - [E \times S]) \times P$$

It: Incidence or mortality rate at year *t*

I0: Incidence or mortality rate at year 0

E: Vaccine efficacy

S: Vaccination coverage

P: Percentage of incidence rate

The time horizon for this analysis was set to six years, with cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA) assessed annually. This approach allowed for a year-by-year evaluation of the vaccination program's impact, providing detailed insights into both short-term and cumulative benefits over the six years. The costs were expressed in 2024 United States Dollars (USD) from the payer's perspective (BPJS Kesehatan), and only direct costs were considered. The capitation rates and tariffs of Indonesia Case-Based Groups (INA-CBGs) provided by BPJS Kesehatan were also used as references to estimate the total costs required for the scenario of the typhoid vaccination program in this study. The typhoid vaccine price of \$34.92 was based on the government contract price with the manufacturer. The vaccine administration and introduction costs were based on previous studies (Suwantika et al. 2021). The vaccination costs include introduction costs, administration costs, and the cost of the vaccine itself. Meanwhile, the costs for the no-vaccination scenario consist of expenses incurred for treating typhoid fever in healthcare facilities in Indonesia, which were based on capitation rates and INA-CBGs tariffs provided by BPJS Kesehatan (Ministry of Health 2023).

Figure 1. Decision tree model.

Data regarding the endpoint cost were reported as incremental cost per morbidity and mortality avoided. The cost of vaccination was calculated over six years to consider the burden of these treatments if it was not applied to the healthcare system. The discount rate was 3% (Marseille et al. 2015).

Budget impact analysis (BIA) applies a top-down costing approach by capturing national long-run average costs (Cunnamo et al. 2016). It takes overall expenditures for each component or input at a central level and then allocated costs using formulae (based on allocation factors such as building usage, staff time, and staff numbers) to estimate unit procedure or service costs (Conteh and Walker 2004; Flessa et al. 2011). In this study, BIA for the six-year time horizon was carried out by projecting the total cost of vaccination each year, with the immunization budget coming from the health budget for each year. The affordability of vaccination costs was determined by considering the incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER) distribution and health outcomes obtained with new interventions. All parameters used in the calculation for CEA and BIA can be seen in Table 1.

Parameters, including epidemiology, costs, and utilities, were extracted from published literature and open-access

databases. The impact of the duration of intervention was considered in scenario analyses. BIA was conducted to evaluate the total cost and the medical cost-saving of a hypothetical nationwide implementation of a potential cost-effective vaccination scenario.

Results

A projection of a six-year horizon, the avoided cases, and saved treatment costs were estimated using the baseline data provided in the parameters. The vaccination program scenario is implemented gradually each year across various regions in Indonesia, targeting the 5–15-year-old population. In the first year, the program focused on one province comprising five cities, reaching a substantial portion of its population, preventing 117 morbidity cases with no recorded mortalities. This finding translated to a significant cost-saving of \$13,730 in avoided treatment expenses. The impact became more pronounced as the program expanded in subsequent years, covering larger populations and more regions. The saved treatment costs were \$204,742, \$454,498, \$2,886,366, \$4,403,502, and \$10,655,063, respectively. More specific information on the avoided cases and saved treatment costs by the targeted population can be seen in Table 2.

The additional cost was quantified by considering avoided cases and deaths to evaluate the cost-effectiveness of the vaccination program. The formula for calculating ICER involves subtracting the total cost incurred with the vaccination from the total cost without vaccination and dividing by the number of avoided cases resulting from the intervention. Total vaccination cost comprises both the intervention costs and the treatment costs. By applying this formula to the provided data, we can analyze the cost-effectiveness of the vaccination program in preventing cases of morbidity and mortality due to typhoid fever over several years. Implementation of typhoid vaccination in Indonesia is considered to be cost-saving. The results of the ICER are provided in Table 3.

Table 1. Parameters used in the model.

Parameters	Value	Reference	CEA/BIA
Epidemiology			
Case Fatality Rate	2.49%	(Pieters et al. 2018)	CEA, BIA
Morbidity Rate	13.7%	(Buckle et al. 2012)	CEA, BIA
Mortality Rate	0.3%	(Buckle et al. 2012)	CEA, BIA
Costs			
Vaccine introduction cost	\$7.324	(Suwantika et al. 2021)	CEA, BIA
Vaccine price per dose	\$34.92		CEA, BIA
Cost of vaccine administration	\$0.5 per individual	(Suwantika et al. 2021)	CEA, BIA
Vaccine characteristics			
Vaccine efficacy	71%	(Appiah et al. 2020)	CEA
ViPS vaccination coverage	80%*	Calculation	CEA, BIA
Schedule interval	3-year		
Others			
Targeted population**	344,381	Calculation	CEA
Discount rate	3%	(WHO 2003)	CEA
Time horizon	6 years		CEA, BIA

*increasing 2,5% annually; **nationwide.

Table 2. ViPS vaccination's targeted coverage avoided cases and saved treatment cost.

Year	Targeted region	Targeted population	Targeted coverage	Vaccination cost	Avoided cases		Saved treatment cost
					Morbidity	Mortality	
1	5	8,277	6,622	\$270,834	117	0	\$13,730
2	6	11,491	9,480	\$368,216	1,741	4	\$204,742
3	9	11,124	9,456	\$388,706	3,863	9	\$454,498
4	22	71,316	62,401	\$2,299,295	24,538	55	\$2,886,366
5	29	103,402	93,062	\$3,401,942	37,435	83	\$4,403,502
6	98	173,909	160,866	\$6,220,989	90,582	201	\$10,655,063

Table 3. Incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER).

Year	Cost without vaccination	Cost with vaccination	Avoided cases		ICER (cost per avoided case)	ICER (cost per avoided death)
			Morbidity	Mortality		
1	\$53,206	\$270,834	117	0	\$1,858	\$217.628
2	\$780,006	\$368,216	1,741	4	Cost-saving	\$54,363
3	\$1,701,198	\$388,706	3,863	9	Cost-saving	Cost-saving
4	\$10,620,381	\$2,299,295	24,538	55	Cost-saving	Cost-saving
5	\$15,933,082	\$3,401,942	37,435	83	Cost-saving	Cost-saving
6	\$15,981,933	\$6,220,989	90,582	201	Cost-saving	Cost-saving

The number of avoided cases gradually increases over time because the population dynamics and the prevalence of the disease in the region directly influence it. According to the prevalence data, the vaccination program is slowly being introduced in Indonesia. In the initial year, the prevalence of the disease is relatively low, resulting in fewer avoided cases. As time progresses, the disease prevalence increases and the vaccination program demonstrates its impact by preventing more cases. This approach ensures that the avoided cases are proportional to the initial disease burden and the growing impact of the vaccination program on the population.

In the six years of the ViPS vaccination program, the introduction of the ViPS vaccine requires various expenses, including social mobilization, information, education, and communication (IEC), training, supervision, and monitoring. Considering the projected national immunization budget, these costs only account for 0.1–2.1% of the overall expenditure. Information about the budget and health impact estimate for typhoid vaccine introduction can be seen in Table 4.

More detailed information about costs within the six-year scenario can be seen in Fig. 2, highlighting that the vaccination program could reduce long-term costs compared to the lack of vaccination. Costs without vaccination scenario rise sharply over time due to the increasing disease burden, treatment costs, diagnostic costs, and associated direct costs can arise because not all healthcare facilities in Indonesia are capable of detecting typhoid, as typhoid fever symptoms often resemble those of common fevers. In contrast, the costs of the vaccination scenario show a more gradual increase, staying significantly lower throughout the observed period. After six years of introduction, the cost of vaccination remains below \$5 million, demonstrating substantial savings despite the initial investment in vaccination.

Taking the ViPS vaccine with the marketed price in Indonesia as a benchmark, the findings affirmed that vaccine coverage, efficacy, mortality rate, and vaccine price are the primary parameters that significantly impact the

Table 4. Budget and health impact estimate for typhoid vaccine introduction.

Outcomes	Vaccination - No vaccination
Number of typhoid cases	(463.035)
Number of hospitalizations	(620.339)
Vaccination costs (vaccines + introduction)	\$13.361.375
Outpatient costs	(\$145.408)
Inpatient costs	(\$45.068.707)
Total costs	(\$31.852.740)

Figure 2. Cost within the six-year scenario.

cost-effectiveness assessment. These parameters can be seen in Fig. 3, indicating that they are influential factors in the budget impact over a six-year time horizon.

Discussion

Typhoid fever presents a substantial public health concern in many LMICs, alongside a rapid rise of antimicrobial-resistant strains of *S. typhi* (WHO 2018). The scarcity of diagnostic tools and surveillance systems complicates the assessment of the prevalence of *S. typhi*, leading to an underestimation of typhoid fever incidence in numerous low-income areas (Marks et al. 2017). WHO advises

Figure 3. One-way Sensitivity Analysis.

incorporating typhoid vaccines into public health programs to control typhoid fever effectively (WHO 2018). In endemic areas, typhoid fever occurs over a broad age range, from the first year of life into adulthood, with incidence peaking in most endemic settings among children aged 5–15 (Meiring et al. 2021). Similarly, in Indonesia, the highest prevalence of typhoid fever is found in the age group of 5–14 years old. In this age group, which comprises school-aged children, there is often a lack of attention to dietary patterns and hygiene (Ministry of Health 2007). Typhoid vaccination programs should be integrated with other strategies aimed at controlling the disease, such as health education, enhancements in water quality and sanitation, and the training of healthcare providers in diagnosing and treating the illness. WHO recommends a one-time single-dose mass catch-up campaign in children up to 15 years of age, prioritizing countries with a high burden of disease or antimicrobial-resistant *S. typhi* (WHO 2018). Modeling studies have confirmed the cost-effectiveness of these combined strategies in high-incidence countries. (Bilcke et al. 2019).

In Indonesia, healthcare providers receive payment through case-based payment (case-mix), which has been in place since 2008 under the national health insurance program. This payment system categorizes diagnoses and procedures based on similarities in clinical characteristics and resource utilization, known as INA-CBGs (Ministry of Health 2016). Even though vaccinations are not yet included in the benefit package of the national health insurance program, there is already a plan to implement this in the future. Given the limited budget, a stepwise nationwide vaccination strategy was applied in this study. The target for immunization was children aged five years in seven provinces with the highest prevalence of typhoid, such as Aceh, Bengkulu, East Kalimantan, West Java, Banten, Central Java, and Central Kalimantan. Regarding the safety, immunogenicity, efficacy, and effectiveness of the ViPS vaccine, data related to these parameters have substantiated their utilization in endemic areas since 2008. A pre-emptive vaccination campaign using the ViPS vaccine, targeting individuals older than two years old, was executed in regions where typhoid was endemic. Furthermore, an assessment of the effectiveness of the ViPS vaccine revealed a 71% reduction in typhoid fever cases associated with ViPS. Therefore, this vaccine significantly controls typhoid outbreaks (Appiah et al. 2020).

The results showed that vaccination can prevent 158,276 cases and 352 deaths in six years. It also could save treatment costs up to \$10,655,063, resulting in a cost-saving intervention. Compared with the routine immunization budget, the total budget for typhoid vaccination would be 0.11%, 0.15%, 0.18%, 0.86%, 1.21% and 2.11%. It can be concluded that the nationwide typhoid vaccination in Indonesia is a cost-saving and affordable intervention since the required budget was only 2.11% of Indonesia's total routine immunization budget. This finding is linear with the results of a previous study by Blicke et al., highlighting Typhoid vaccination is efficient in countries with high incidence and significant treatment costs since it maximizes health benefits relative to investment (Bilcke et al. 2019). Another study in Bangladesh also mentioned that nationwide routine immunization with catch-up campaigns is highly cost-effective and even cost-saving when considering societal costs, including medical, non-medical, and productivity costs (Weyant et al. 2024). Additionally, a study by Cook et al. summarized that the typhoid Vi vaccine is economically justifiable in high-incidence areas like Kolkata, Karachi, and North Jakarta (Cook et al. 2008).

By referring to the cost over time with the sensitivity analysis, it becomes clear that the cost-effectiveness of vaccination depends on parameters such as vaccine price, administration costs, and coverage levels. This can occur because vaccination is indeed quite costly at the beginning. However, it can significantly reduce typhoid treatment costs and help control antibiotic resistance when linked to long-term effects and herd immunity. However, by optimizing vaccine pricing and coverage, policymakers can achieve significant cost savings while minimizing the public health burden over time.

This study was intended to provide critical evidence for policymakers in Indonesia, where typhoid fever is not included in the routine vaccination schedule despite its significant burden and high cost of illness. Typhoid remains a major public health concern, with a lack of detection of typhoid, often misjudged, and a substantial number of cases leading to considerable morbidity, mortality, and economic strain on both individuals and the healthcare system. The economic and health impacts of introducing typhoid vaccination in routine immunization programs can be evaluated by conducting CEA. The CEA will compare the costs of vaccination

against the savings from reduced healthcare costs and fewer hospitalizations. It will also assess the potential reduction in typhoid-related morbidity and mortality, allowing policymakers to weigh the benefits of vaccination relative to its costs. The results of this study offer crucial data to inform decisions on resource allocation and public health strategies, highlighting the potential for substantial cost savings and improved health outcomes. Eventually, this analysis seeks to guide the inclusion of typhoid vaccines in the national immunization program, cost-effectively addressing a major health issue and improving overall public health.

Even though this study has several significant findings, it also has several limitations. Probabilistic sensitivity analysis was not included in this study. Nevertheless, a one-way sensitivity analysis was applied to investigate the most influential parameter impacting the ICER. In addition, the decision-making model was static, which assumes a fixed population level, typically based on current vaccination coverage or historical data. This model has limitations in capturing the dynamic nature of population immunity and the long-term benefits of herd immunity. Dynamic models incorporating temporal dynamics and population interactions may offer a more comprehensive understanding of the herd effect and its implications for public health decision-making. Meanwhile, static decision models can provide valuable insights into the short-term impacts of interventions. Considering the lack of economic evaluation studies on ViPs in Indonesia, we expect this study to assist stakeholders in deciding to include ViPs as a public program in Indonesia.

Conclusions

The nationwide typhoid vaccination in Indonesia is a cost-saving and affordable intervention since the required budget was only 2.11% of Indonesia's total routine immunization budget.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

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Author contributions

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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